

REFLECTION OF TEACHING OF GEETA IN INDIAN CONSTITUTION

by

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ABSTRACT

There are a lot of similarities between the Indian Constitution and Geeta. Both seek to establish a society that is equal and just where human beings can lead peaceful lives and pursue their goals in life. Equality, justice, and people's welfare are central themes of both the Indian Constitution and Geeta. The law aims at providing a just society where the rights of individuals can be realized. One of the most important functions of the state is to evolve a legal system that can ensure justice. Spirituality aims at realising the divine potential of all human beings and inculcating the feelings of oneness and universal brotherhood. The message of oneness and universal brotherhood has the potential to provide a just society where people can live their lives peacefully. The article explores the parallels between Geeta's teachings and the concepts enshrined in the Indian Constitution.

Introduction.

There are a lot of similarities between the Indian Constitution and Geeta. Both seek to establish a society that is equal and just where human beings can lead peaceful lives and pursue their goals in life. Equality, justice, and people's welfare are central themes of both the Indian Constitution and Geeta. The law is a man-made set of rules that govern the relationships between our various physical bodies and serve as a means of resolving conflicts between them. Law aims at providing a just society where rights of the individuals can be realized¹. Spirituality refers to that which is common and unites all of humanity, despite our separate physical bodies and circumstances. It can also be called "transcendental unity." As a result, law and spirituality are fundamentally intertwined. Although the law focuses on our separate bodies and spirituality focuses on the unseen that unites us, they are interactive and mutually dependent constructs because the human experience is paradoxically both of being separate and together. Therefore, peace and happiness tend to flourish where spirituality is upheld by law and where law, though carefully defined to protect the individual, is imbued with an awareness of the concomitant spirituality of the individual. On the other hand, we tend to find conflicts and wars where the law denies or comes into conflict with spirituality, or where spirituality has lost its legal support.²

Ensuring Justice : Aim of Constitution and Geeta.

Justice as an ideal has a spiritual significance which expresses spiritual humanism and is the ultimate goal of our civilization. Justice is the central theme of our Constitution. The Constitution provides social, economic and political justice to all citizens. It also provides for the creation of an egalitarian society based on liberty, equality and fraternity through the instrument of law.³ The law provides for the rights and the duties and expects people to follow the duties which have been provided by the law. When someone violates the law and cause loss to another then law comes into action and the offender is brought before the court room where judgement is delivered according to the prior deeds of the person who violated the law. When we look at law and its enforcement

¹ V.D. Mahajan, Jurisprudence & Legal Theory 115 (Eastern Book Company, Lucknow, 5th edn., 2016).

² Law and Spirituality, available at <http://www.jameskimmeljr.com/law/law-and-spirituality/> (Visited on Jan 12, 2022).

³ A. K. Sikri, Spirituality and the legal profession, Sunday Guardian Live, May 2, 2020.

from this lens then we realize that this is not different from the doctrine of karma which is prevalent in spiritual traditions.⁴

Equality: Basic feature of Constitution and Geeta.

Right to equality is one of the basic features of law and spirituality also considers that everyone is equal. Law considers everyone equal before the eyes of the law and spirituality considers everyone equal before the God. Our Constitution provides fundamental right to equality.⁵ Our Constitution provides that everyone shall be treated equally before the law irrespective of his gender, economic status or any other considerations. Spirituality also provides that everyone is ultimately one reality in the highest analysis and everyone is equal irrespective of their gender, age, nationality etc and consequently everyone should be treated equally with compassion. The basic spiritual values and fundamental principles of the law enshrined in our Constitution are the same, but the law is being improved and developed towards more socially acceptable guidelines for the benefit of society as a whole and in this process spirituality has much to contribute.

Balanced philosophy of life.

The Bhagavad Gita advocates a balanced philosophy of life. There are two paths in human life—Pravritti, the path of action and progress, and Nivritti, the path of spiritual perfection. Through Pravritti, a welfare society is established by improving the economy and political systems. Progress in society mandatorily implies the united efforts of its people. Cooperation, togetherness, and mutual love and understanding are the hallmarks of Pravritti, leading to a state called Abhyudaya. Through Nivritti, a value-oriented life is achieved, which is based on the inner spiritual dimensions of humanity. The hallmarks of Nivritti are a change in attitude towards one's own self, towards life and situations, towards other people, work, and the concentration and purification of the mind.⁶ Both outward actions and internal peace are equally required for establishment of a happy society. Material prosperity without ethical way of life is not sustainable and material prosperity ignored totally is bound to lead to inaction. This balanced approach has been emphasized in Geeta.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Article 14, Constitution of India, 1950.

⁶ Swami Yadavendrananda, Where the two paths meet: Krishna's message in the Bhagavad Gita, The Hindu, Aug 30, 2018.

The Indian Constitution emphasises a balanced approach to life. The Indian constitution aims at balancing individual interests with societal interests. There is an attempt to reconcile individual and group rights. The Indian constitution recognises that a just society can't be established when there is a lack of a balancing of interests.

Role of Spirituality in Averting Crime.

In the modern world, many crimes are attributed to the wrong way of living. The modern world has become too matter-oriented, where sense pleasures and material possessions define happiness. The way to measure success in this modern world is by the amount of money and material possessions one has. In today's world, people don't have time to talk to themselves and think about the bigger and more fundamental questions. In such a scenario, self-alienation increases and meaninglessness creeps in. It has been noted that such meaninglessness in life, where one doesn't have anything more important to do, leads to frustration, which in turn results in crime. When society considers material possessions and money as the only means of success and happiness, the younger generation often tries to have money and material possessions, and for this reason, they often choose paths that go against the dictates of the law. Our modern society has not been able to teach people that there is something higher and bigger that one should seek. People try to satisfy themselves and become happy by trying sensual transient pleasures, and when these pleasures are not able to satisfy them any more, they indulge in various affairs, which again goes against the mandate of the law. Spirituality has the potential to provide an alternative to this present situation. Spirituality provides that there is some higher truth which should be discovered by everyone and provides guidance for achieving the same. Spiritual traditions of the east and west teach that humans are not limited creatures but infinite if they realise their truth, which is hidden. Spiritual traditions have always maintained this position that the meaning of life is not just sense pleasures but something more than this, and without realising the ultimate truth, a human being can't be totally fulfilled. Many of the problems that the law faces can be solved if the teachings of spiritual traditions are understood and spirituality is understood as a way of life. Fear of the law or fear of God can't always stop a person from committing a crime. Spirituality teaches universal brotherhood, love, and compassion, and if these teachings are internalized, then they can lead to a better and safer society.

Egalitarian society and Geeta.

Both the Indian Constitution and Geeta aim at establishing an egalitarian society. We live in an age that cherishes equality of opportunity for all and celebrates the breaking down of barriers such as race. Intriguingly, a similar egalitarian spirit is enshrined in the Bhagavad-gita, written millennia ago. The Gita boldly declares that all people, whatever their social position, can take shelter from God and attain the supreme destination. Social liberalism as an ideology recognizes the market economy but at the same time broadens the role of government in reducing social inequalities on the basis of the principles of social justice for the proper functioning of capitalism. Therefore, the principles of justice, equality and freedom, as well as secularism, constitute the central elements of the constitutional ideology of social liberalism in India. The founding fathers of our constitution envisioned an egalitarian society based on such ideal principles.

Geeta and Indian Secularism.

The Indian Constitution and the Indian state are passionately wedded to the ideal of freedom — freedom of thought and conscience and freedom to profess and practise the faith of one's choice, and even freedom to live without a faith. The freedoms granted and guaranteed by the Indian state are meant to ensure the all-round growth of the Indian people through stimulation of their thinking and initiative.⁷ A secular state so conceived, one that is not wedded either to religious indifference or anti-religious atheism, but impartially promotes all religions, believing in the spiritual dimension of the human personality over and above his sensate nature, is a unique phenomenon with a prophetic role to play.⁸ The teaching of Geeta is all-embracing and inclusive, devoid of any dogma.

Conclusion.

There are a lot of similarities between the Indian Constitution and Geeta. Both seek to establish a society that is equal and just where human beings can lead peaceful lives and pursue their goals in life. Equality, justice, and people's welfare are central themes of both the Indian Constitution and Geeta. Both Geeta and the Indian constitution seek to ensure justice and lead to a society that is equal. Both Geeta and the Constitution advocate a balanced philosophy of life. The establishment

⁷ Swami Ranganathananda, The message of the upanishads 59(Advaita Ashrama ,Kolkata ,1st edn.,2019).

⁸ Swami Ranganathananda, The message of the upanishads 60(Advaita Ashrama ,Kolkata ,1st edn.,2019).

of an egalitarian society has been an important consideration in both Geeta and the Indian constitution. The concept of Indian secularism has been influenced by the teachings of the Geeta.

